

Fabrication of Carbon/PEEK Composites Tubes and Their Energy Absorption Performance

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ABSTRACT

Carbon/PEEK composite tubes were fabricated under different cooling conditions by using a recently developed fabrication system which employs thermal expandable PTFE mandrel. Three kinds of the cooling conditions were used: rapidly-cooling (95.5°C/min.), gradually-cooling (8.2°C/min.) and slowly-cooling (0.7°C/min.). The energy absorption characteristics were evaluated.

It was shown that composite tubes can be fabricated irrespective of the cooling rate. The specific energy absorption value of rapidly-cooled composite tubes was only 10% higher than that of gradually- and slowly-cooled composite tubes. However, all composite tubes displayed the higher energy absorption values compared to those values reported in the literature.

Key Words: Carbon/PEEK composite tube, new fabrication system, cooling rate, energy absorption, crushing

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently composite materials have been found to display better specific energy absorption capabilities compared to conventional metallic materials. Energy absorption research of composite materials has been carried out on various material systems. However, relatively a little work on the energy absorption of thermoplastic-matrix composites has been reported, largely because of the difficulty of producing high quality tubes using continuous fiber materials. Sato has recently developed a method for fabrication of carbon/PEEK composite tubes using UD-prepregs and a thermally expandable PTFE (polytetrafluoroethylene) mandrel⁽¹⁾. In our previous work⁽²⁾, it was found that carbon/PEEK composite tubes which were fabricated by this recently developed fabrication method displayed excellent energy absorption values. This was attributed to the high interlaminar fracture toughness of PEEK-matrix composites. PEEK is semi-crystalline polymer and therefore the microstructure and the mechanical properties (especially fracture toughness) of carbon/PEEK composite depend strongly on the cooling condition. The fracture toughness decreases with decreasing cooling rate⁽³⁾⁻⁽⁷⁾.

In this study, carbon/PEEK composite tubes were fabricated under different cooling conditions. The quality of these composite tubes and their energy absorption has been evaluated. The effect of cooling rate on the energy absorption is discussed.

2.FABRICATION

2.1 Fabrication of carbon/PEEK composite tubes

The material used in this study was unidirectional carbon/PEEK prepreg sheet of APC-2/AS4 (ICI-Fiberite Co.,). Carbon/PEEK composite tubes were fabricated by employing an internal pressure induced by thermal expansion of a PTFE mandrel⁽¹⁾. This fabrication system consists of PTFE mandrel, cylindrical preform of APC-2 and outer mold (Fig.1). Detailed fabrication method is described as follows.

1) Prepreg sheets were cut into rectangular shape, laminated and preformed by wrapping into a cylindrical shape. Twenty laminated layers were used and the fibers were oriented at $\pm 15^\circ$ to the longitudinal axis of the tube.

2) The APC-2 preform was placed on the PTFE mandrel and both were inserted into an outer mold of metal or ceramics pipe. This state was called the set-up.

3) The set-up was placed in a heat convection oven which was previously heated at 380°C. The hold time of the set-up in the high temperature oven was 120 minutes. In this process, PTFE undergoes a large thermal expansion which was thermally stable. As a result of this unique characterization, the mandrel expands sufficiently enough to fix the preform and to squeeze out the interlaminar voids. The fixing pressure was 0.3MPa at 380°C⁽¹⁾, which is relatively low and constant. Then the set-up was cooled down to room temperature, in this study the different cooling conditions were chosen as described in 2.2.

Fig.1 Components used to make tubes.

2.2 Cooling rates during consolidation

The cooling conditions are shown in Table 1. Three kinds of cooling conditions were chosen; (1)immersion into chilled water (rapidly-cooled), (2)cooling in air (gradually-cooled) and (3)left in the oven and the heater was switched off (slowly-cooled). The cooling rate was determined as the rate from 380°C to T_g (143°C) was measured by thermocouples embedded between 10ply and 11ply. The cooling rates are given in Table 1. In the case of rapidly-cooled samples, the cooling rates was higher than 30°C/min., which was recommended by ICI.

Table 1 Cooling conditions

	Rapidly-cooled	Gradually-Cooled	Slowly-Cooled
Cooling Method	immersion in chilled water	cooled in air	left in oven and with heater switched off
Cooling Rate (°C/min.)	95.5	8.2	0.7

2.3 Quality of the composite tubes

Fig.2 shows the appearance of a rapidly-cooled composite tube. A very smooth surface was obtained without additional surface processing. There are no wrinkles and no disorder of fiber orientation. Fig.3 shows a photomicrograph of a cross section of a rapidly-cooled composite tube. The tube is free from delamination and has a very low void content. Hence excellent consolidation was obtained through this fabrication method. High quality composite tubes were also obtained in gradually- and slowly-cooling conditions. Tubes were whiter with decreasing cooling rate; this may be caused by the different crystallinity of the PEEK-matrix. In rapidly- and gradually-cooled composite tubes, the tube had an internal diameter of 47.6mm and a wall thickness of about 2.7mm, whereas slowly-cooled tubes had an internal diameter of 46.0mm and a wall thickness of about 2.8mm, although the same outer mold was used. The variation of tube wall thickness was attributed to the different shrinkage under different cooling conditions.

50mm

0.1mm

Fig.2 Appearance of rapidly-cooled tube. Fig.3 Photomicrograph of cross-section of rapidly-cooled tube.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW (Effect of cooling rate on fracture toughness of carbon/PEEK composites)

PEEK is a semi-crystalline polymer, so that the degree of crystallinity and the mechanical properties of carbon/PEEK composites depend on the cooling condition. The effect of cooling rate on the fracture toughness of carbon/PEEK composite has been discussed by Talbott et al⁽³⁾, Curtis et al⁽⁴⁾, Lustiger et al⁽⁵⁾, Davies et al⁽⁶⁾ and Vautey⁽⁷⁾. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness (GIC) was examined using a double cantilever beam test and a center notched tensile test. The effect of cooling rate on GIC is shown in Fig.3. The GIC value reduces with decreasing cooling rate. According to Talbott et al⁽³⁾, GIC values of specimens cooled at a rate higher than 2000°C/min. are twice that of 2.8°C/min. cooled specimen. According to Curtis et al⁽⁴⁾, Lustiger et al⁽⁵⁾ and Vautey⁽⁷⁾, GIC values of fast cooled specimens are 35%, 25%, 27% higher than that of slower cooled (1°C/min.) specimens, respectively. However, according to Davies et al⁽⁶⁾ the effect of cooling rate on fracture toughness is negligible. Very slowly cooled (0.3 or 1°C/min.) specimens showed unstable crack propagation and this is an indication of highly reduced toughness.

Fig.4 Relation between GIC and cooling rate.

4. ENERGY ABSORPTION

Energy absorption capability of carbon/PEEK composite tubes were investigated and the effect of cooling rate on the energy absorption are discussed.

4.1 Experimental procedure

Composite tube specimens 55mm long were cut from the long tubes. To initiate progressive crushing a 45° chamfer was lathe turned onto one end of the tube. The tubes were tested in axial compression using a 250 kN Shimadzu Autograph twin-screw driven machine at constant cross-head speed of 5mm/min.. The crush zone morphology was studied using optical microscopy. The specific energy absorption (Es) was calculated as the ratio of the mean crush load obtained from the load-displacement trace and the mass per unit length of the composite tube.

4.2 Results and Discussion

Typical load-displacement traces for each cooling condition are shown in Fig.5. During initial stages of crushing the load increased rapidly to a peak value of about 100kN (point A in fig.5). After the initial peak the load dropped at point B and then increased before the load reaches at a constant value, which is known as progressive crushing load. Progressive crushing occurred in all the specimens but there were some differences. The load at point B and the mean crush load in rapidly-cooled specimens were higher than that in the other specimens. The load uniformity in rapidly-cooled specimens was also superior to that in other specimens.

The results of the crushing tests are summarized in Table 1. These Es values were approximately twice as high as values for carbon/Epoxy (110kJ/kg)⁽⁸⁾ and were the highest values ever recorded for any composite material. Es of rapidly-cooled specimens was 10% higher than that of gradually- and slowly-cooled specimens.

Fig.6 shows the appearance of each tested specimen. The tubes crushed by splaying of the tube wall into internal and external fronds, known as the splaying mode⁽⁸⁾. At the end of crushing the fronds did not spring back when the platen was removed. Crushing appearances were brittle in specimens cooled at the lower rates with some fragmentations of the internal and external fronds.

Fig.5 Load-displacement curves of each specimen.

Table 2 Energy absorption performances of each specimen

	Mean Crush Load (kN)	Mean Crush Stress (MPa)	Specific Energy Absorption (Es) (kJ/kg)
Rapidly-Cooled	148.7	348.7	220.7
	143.7	332.6	211.8
	149.5	358.4	224.0
			as averaged (218.8)
Gradually-Cooled	134.5	308.8	197.9
	132.3	309.6	194.7
	132.3	317.3	198.0
			(196.9)
Slowly-Cooled	142.5	320.4	199.0
	139.9	315.8	196.2

Fig.6 Appearances of tested specimens.

Fig.7 shows a photomicrograph of the crush zone morphology of rapidly-cooled specimen. The tube wall splits into internal and external fronds separated by a debris wedge. The central crack of the tube wall was very short (less than 1mm). Kink band were observed at the tip of debris wedge. The fronds were bent over a sharp radius of curvature. Many delaminations were observed in both the internal and external fronds. Fiber fractures occurred in the inside and outside of the tube wall in the compression side of the beam. This is caused by large flexural stress on the compression side of the beam. Figs.8 and 9 show the photomicrographs of the crush zone morphologies of gradually- and slowly-cooled specimens, respectively. The crush zone morphologies of gradually- and slowly-cooled specimens were similar to that of rapidly-cooled specimen.

In our previous work it was shown that the composite tubes with higher fracture toughness displayed higher E_s . In this study, progressive crushing behavior is influenced by the different fracture toughness caused by different cooling rates. The load uniformity of the high constant load in rapidly-cooled specimen was superior compared to the other specimens. E_s values of rapidly-cooled specimens were higher than gradually- and slowly-cooled specimens. Fronds showed more brittleness at the cooling rate decreased. These are indications of reduced toughness at lower cooling rate. However, there is little difference in crush zone morphology between rapidly-cooled specimen and specimens cooled at lower rates. E_s values of these specimens are the highest ever recorded for any composite material. The 10% change of E_s value with cooling rate is lower than that of change in $G_{IC}^{(3)-(7)}$ with cooling rate. In other words the E_s is less influenced by cooling rate.

Rapidly-Cooled

Fig.7 Crush zone morphology of rapidly-cooled specimen.

Gradually-Cooled

Fig.8 Crush zone morphology of gradually-cooled specimen.

Slowly-Cooled

Fig.9 Crush zone morphology of slowly-cooled specimen.

5. CONCLUSION

It was shown that good quality carbon/PEEK composite tubes can be fabricated under different cooling conditions by using PTFE thermally expandable mandrel technique. The effect of cooling rate on the Es can be summarized as follows.

Composite tubes subjected to rapid cooling displayed Es values 10% higher than tubes cooled at low rates. However, irrespective of cooling condition, all the composite tubes displayed higher Es compared to values reported for other composite systems.

References

1. H.Sato and H.Hirakawa., Proc. of 2nd Japan International SAMPE Symposium, pp.951-958, 1991
2. H.Hamada, J.C.Coppola, D.Hull, Z.Maekawa and H.Sato., Composites, Vol.23, No.4, pp.245-252, 1992
3. M.F.Talbott, G.S.Springer and L.A.Berglund., Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.21, pp.1056-1081, 1987
4. P.T.Curtis, P.Davies, I.K.Partridge and P.Sainty., Proc. of ICCM6/ECCM2, London, pp.4.401-4.412, 1987
5. A.Lustiger, F.S.Uralil and G.M.Newaz., Polymer Composites, Vol.22, No.1, pp.65-75, 1990
6. P.Davies, W.Cantwell, H.Richard, C.Moulin and H.H.Kausch., Proc. of ECCM3, pp.747-752, 1989
7. P.Vautey., SAMPE Quaternary, Vol.21, No.2, pp.23-38, 1990
8. D.Hull., Composites Science and Technology, Vol.40, pp.377-422, 1992